

Synthesis of 3,4-Dihydropyrido (3,4-b) benzindoles using Polyphosphate Ester as a Cyclising Agent

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β -[Benz(e)- and benz(g)indol-3-yl]ethylamines have been reacted with benzoyl chloride, acetic anhydride and formamide to yield the respective amides. These amides have been cyclised with polyphosphate ester (PPE) to the corresponding 1-substituted 3,4-dihydropyrido-(3,4-b)benzindoles (β -carbolines) in 60-70% yields.

AMONG the four types of carbolines, β -carboline is the well investigated molecule, since it is the basic structural unit for a large number of indole alkaloids^{1,2}. Studies on the synthesis of benzo- β -carbolines are limited only to benz-substitution in the pyridine ring of the carboline molecule. Recently polyphosphate ester is becoming a very popular cyclising agent³ because of its advantages over other acidic cyclising agents, such as improved yields and mild conditions. This reagent was used in this laboratory for the synthesis of 3,4-dihydro- ν -carbolines⁴. We now report the synthesis of several Bz-benz-substituted β -carbolines in order to test the generality of the use of PPE as an acidic cyclising agent in the Bischler-Napieralski type of cyclodehydration.

The generally accepted synthesis of 3,4-dihydropyrido(3,4-b)indoles involves the cyclodehydration of acyl derivatives of β -(indol-3-yl)ethylamines (tryptamines)^{5,6}. In continuation of our work⁷ on synthesis with benzindoles, the β -[benz(e)- and benz(g)indol-3-yl]ethylamines, required as the starting materials for the present synthesis, have been prepared from benzindole-3-carboxaldehydes⁸. These tryptamines⁹ (1 & 4) have been allowed to react with benzoyl chloride, acetic anhydride-acetic acid and formamide to get the respective amides (2 & 5) (Table 1). The amides on cyclisation with PPE¹⁰ in dry chloroform gave the corresponding 1-substituted-3,4-dihydropyrido(3,4-b)benzindoles (Table 2) in 60-70% yields.

The compounds (3b and 3c) showed the UV maxima at λ_{max} nm (log ϵ) 225 (7.5), 253 (6.6), 230 (9.0), and 255 (7.7). The IR spectra of the carbolines showed

*For correspondence

TABLE 1

Amides of benz(e)- & benz(g) tryptamines	2a	*2b	*2c	5a	5b	*5c
m.p. (°C)	128	—	—	205	120	—
Nature (solvent)	Colourless needles (aq. ethanol)	—	—	Colourless needles (aq. ethanol)	Brown plates (benzene)	—
Found (%)	C 80.4 H 5.5 N 8.7	—	—	80.3 5.8 8.4	76.3 6.4 11.4	—
Mol. formula	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ N ₂ O	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₂ O	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₂ O	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ N ₂ O	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₂ O	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₂ O
Calc. (%)	C 80.2 H 5.8 N 8.9	—	—	80.2 5.8 8.9	76.2 6.4 11.1	—
Yield (%)	95	90	64	97	92	98
uv λ_{max} nm (log ϵ)	230(3.6) 250(2.6)	—	—	260(1.7) 280(0.52)	—	—
ir cm ⁻¹	ν NH 3350(broad) ν CO 1610s	ν NH 3400w ν CO 1610m	ν NH 3420w ν CO 1610w (CHCl ₃)	ν NH 3500s ν CO 1650s (CHCl ₃)	—	—

* Since these compounds were semi-solids, they were directly taken for the next step.

the NH frequency around 3400 cm^{-1} . In the NMR spectrum of compound (3b), the methylene protons at positions 3 and 4 of the pyridine residue are observed in the regions $7.6\text{--}8.2\tau$ and $6.4\text{--}7.4\tau$, respectively. The signal due to methyl protons at position 1 appears at 8.4τ , as expected. The six aromatic protons along with the proton on the nitrogen give rise to a complicated spectrum observed in the region $2.0\text{--}2.7\tau$.¹¹

Experimental

The UV spectra were recorded on Beckmann DB spectrometer in methanol and IR spectra on Perkin-Elmer infracord in nujol. The NMR spectrum was recorded on a Varian A-60 spectrometer in CDCl_3 using TMS as an internal reference at 60 Mc. PPE was prepared according to the literature method.³

Only the general methods for the experimental procedure are given.

1. Benzoylation of β -[benz(e) and benz(g) indol-3-yl] ethylamines (1 & 4)

The appropriate ethylamine (0.0056 mole) was taken in a conical flask. Benzoyl chloride (2 ml, 0.013 mole) and sodium hydroxide (40 ml, 10%) were added to it. The mixture was shaken with occasional cooling with ice-cold water for about 30–40 min. It was kept overnight in a refrigerator. The solid that separated was filtered and washed with water several times. The benzoyl derivatives (2a & 5a) crystallised from aqueous ethanol in colourless needles.

TABLE 2

3,4-Dihydropyrido-(3,4-b)benzindoles	3a	3b	3c	6a	6b	6c(picrate)
m.p. (°C)	158	135-9	204-6	219	209	175-9
Nature (solvent)	dark needles (benzene)	deep brown needles (aq.dioxane)	brown needles (aq.dioxane)	yellow needles (benzene)	yellow needles (benzene)	brown needles (benzene)
Found (%)	C 85.3 H 5.3 N 9.8	81.9 5.8 11.6	81.5 5.5 12.6	85.4 5.4 9.7	81.9 5.9 11.2	56.3 3.9 15.2
Mol. formula	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₂	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₂	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₂	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₂	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₂	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ N ₅ O ₇
Calc. (%)	C 85.1 H 5.4 N 9.5	82.0 6.0 11.9	81.8 5.5 12.7	85.1 5.4 9.5	82.0 6.0 11.4	56.1 3.4 15.6
Yield (%)	69	70	63	64	62	68
uv λ _{max} nm (log ε)		225(7.5), 253(6.6)	230(9.0), 255(7.7)			
ir cm ⁻¹	νNH 3400w νC=C 1610w, 1700w	νNH 3400w νC=C 1620w, 1580w	νNH 3400w νC=C 1620w, 1580w	νNH 3420w νC=C 1650w, 1550w	νNH 3400w νC=C 1650w, 1700w	νNH 3400w νC=C 1680s 1550w

2. Acetylation of β-[benz(e) and benz(g) indol-3-yl] ethylamines

The tryptamine (0.0057 mole) was taken in a round bottom flask (50 ml) fitted with a reflux condenser. Acetic anhydride (1 ml) and acetic acid (0.5 ml) were added to it. The mixture was gently heated for about 5 min and cooled. About 10 ml of cold water was added to decompose the excess reagent. The product was collected either by filtration or extraction.

3. Formylation of β-[benz(e) and benz(g) indol-3-yl] ethylamines

A mixture of the amine (0.0053 mole) and formamide (1 g) was heated at 180° (bath temp.) for 4 hr. Removal of the excess formamide *in vacuo* left a brown oil which was taken in chloroform. The extract was washed twice with hydrochloric acid (10%), then with sodium bicarbonate (10%) and finally dried (Na₂SO₄). The solvent was evaporated *in vacuo* to get the Nβ-formyl benzindol-3-(2'-yl ethylamines) (2c & 5c) as greenish semi-solids.

4. PPE cyclisation of the amides (2a-c & 5a-c)

A solution of the amide (0.0046 mole) and PPE (4 g) in dry chloroform (25 ml) was refluxed for 1 hr. After removal of the solvent *in vacuo*, cold water was added to the reaction mixture under ice-cooling. It was stirred for 2 hr to effect complete decomposition of the reagent. The solution was washed with

ether to remove the non-basic material and the aqueous layer made alkaline with sodium hydroxide (10%). The product that separated was collected either by filtration or extraction. The 3,4-dihydropyrido(3,4-b)benzindoles, thus obtained, are described in Table 2.

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